

D7.1 Website, project logo and social media

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Document Control Sheet

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Introduction

A strong visual and digital identity is a key asset in the communication and dissemination of the REMEDY project. As a primary point of contact for many stakeholders, it is essential that the project's branding and online presence create a professional, recognizable, and engaging identity that attracts attention and fosters meaningful interaction.

To establish this, the project has developed three essential elements for its digital presence and outreach:

- A project website, serving as the central platform for sharing research updates, key outcomes, and resources.
- A project logo, which provides a consistent visual identity across all communication materials.
- A cohesive visual strategy, ensuring consistent branding and communication across all materials.
- A LinkedIn presence, enabling direct engagement with researchers, industry professionals, and the wider public.

This document outlines the development of these elements, their current status, and the strategy for maintaining and expanding the project's digital visibility over its duration.

Project website

The official REMEDY website serves as the primary platform for sharing project updates, research outcomes, and key information with stakeholders. It offers straightforward access to project objectives, work packages, publications, and events, enhancing transparency and visibility.

The website is located at:

<https://eic-remedy.eu/>

The domain eic-remedy.eu was chosen to align with the project acronym (REMEDY) and its affiliation with the EIC Pathfinder program, ensuring consistency and easy recognition.

Figure 1. REMEDY website homepage

The website was launched at the beginning of February 2025, developed by InnoRenew CoE, and is actively maintained by the same team to ensure regular updates and content management. The platform was designed to be user-friendly, informative, and accessible, engaging diverse audiences, including researchers, industry professionals, general public and policymakers.

The EIC REMEDY website is structured to provide clear and structured access to project information. The main sections include:

- About (Home Page) – serves as the main landing page, introducing the project’s objectives, research vision, and key information. It provides an overview of the project’s goals, background, and significance.
- Consortium – introduces all project partners, including links to their respective websites, and further details the roles and contributions of the teams from each partner organization.
- News – a section featuring announcements, updates, and project-related activities to keep audiences informed.
- Contact – Provides contact details for inquiries, collaboration opportunities, and communication with the project team.
- EIC ELMs Portfolio – Showcases project-related outputs and key results, presenting ongoing research, findings, and contributions to the field of Engineered Living Materials (ELMs).

To ensure the website remains an effective and dynamic dissemination tool, the InnoRenew CoE team is responsible for regular updates and content management. As the central public-facing platform, the website plays a key role in strengthening the project's visibility, credibility, and stakeholder engagement.

Future content updates will include:

- New publications and open-access materials to share research findings.
- Project updates and partner activities to keep stakeholders informed.
- Relevant announcements related to dissemination and engagement opportunities.

Additionally, the project team will implement methods to track website activity and improve its visibility, including basic visitor statistics and content performance monitoring, to keep the website relevant and engaging for the scientific, industrial, and policymaking communities.

Project logo

A strong visual identity is essential for ensuring recognition and consistency across all project communications. The EIC REMEDY logo was designed to reflect the project's scientific vision, technological innovation, and interdisciplinary approach, maintaining a balance between clarity, professionalism, and modern aesthetics.

The logo serves as a visual representation of REMEDY's core mission, integrating biotechnology, architecture, and sustainability. It combines scientific precision and architectural elements, making it recognizable and effective across various communication channels.

Figure 2. Official REMEDY logo

The REMEDY logo consists of distinct components that symbolize key aspects of the project:

- Letter "R" with DNA strand – represents synthetic biology, microbiome research, and biotechnological innovation at the core of REMEDY's approach.
- Letter "M" shaped as buildings – symbolizes the architectural application of Engineered Living Materials (ELMs), highlighting the project's focus on transforming built environments.
- Circuit-like design in "E" – reflects the integration of digital tools, computational modeling, and smart biofabrication techniques within the project.
- Tagline "Building Tomorrow with Living Architecture" – highlights the project's biofabrication vision, where microbiomes become integral to architectural design.

To maintain visual consistency, the REMEDY follows a defined color palette and typography:

- Primary Green (#006854) – represents sustainability, biofabrication, and ecological balance. Consistent color use, maintaining a clean and modern aesthetic.
- Modern, geometric font – selected for clarity, professionalism, and an innovative appearance.

The REMEDY logo effectively combines elements of biology, engineering, and architecture, making it a strong visual representation of the project's interdisciplinary nature.

Logo variants and usage

To ensure flexibility and consistency across various communication materials, the REMEDY logo has been designed in multiple formats to accommodate different applications.

Figure 3. REMEDY logo variants: Left: primary logo. Right: simplified logo.

Primary logo

The primary logo serves as the official representation of the REMEDY project across all formal and high-visibility communications. It retains all key design elements, ensuring full brand recognition. This version is used in:

- Official documents, reports, and presentations,
- The project website and online platforms,
- High-resolution print materials.

Simplified logo

The simplified logo is a streamlined adaptation designed for use where space is limited. It retains the core identity of the project and is suitable for:

- Small-scale digital use (e.g., favicons, icons, social media profile pictures),
- Branded materials where a minimalist approach is preferred,
- Compact layouts where the full logo would be difficult to read.

Minimum size recommendation

For applications smaller than 20 mm in height, the logo should be used without the tagline to maintain readability.

By offering these logo variations, the REMEDY project ensures versatility across different media, preserving readability and impact in all contexts.

Logo placement and background usage

To ensure consistent branding across different communication materials, the REMEDY logo must be placed on backgrounds that provide sufficient contrast for readability.

Figure 4. REMEDY logo background variations. Left: full-color logo on a white background (preferred primary usage). Right: white logo on a dark background for high contrast.

Preferred usage (light backgrounds)

- The full-color logo should be placed on white or light backgrounds, ensuring maximum clarity and maintaining the integrity of its original colors.

Alternative usage (dark backgrounds)

- When placed on dark backgrounds, a white version of the logo should be used to ensure visibility.

Black and white logo usage

In situations where color printing is not available or when a high-contrast version is required, the REMEDY logo is also available in black and white versions. This ensures clarity and recognizability while maintaining the logo's integrity.

Figure 5. REMEDY black and white logo variants. Left: Black logo on a white background for monochrome printing. Right: White logo on a black background for high-contrast applications.

The black and white version is available in two formats, depending on the background:

- Black logo on a white background – Suitable for official documents, reports, and monochrome printing where color reproduction is not possible.

- White logo on a black background – Designed for high-contrast applications, such as embossed materials, promotional items, and dark-mode digital assets.

Logo usage guidelines

To maintain visual consistency and brand integrity, the REMEDY logo must be used in accordance with predefined guidelines. Misuse or improper modifications can weaken recognition and reduce the effectiveness of project communication.

Figure 6. Incorrect logo usage examples

Prohibited modifications

- Distortion or resizing – the logo must always be scaled proportionally. Stretching or compressing it distorts its appearance and should be avoided.
- Altering colors – the logo must only be used in its approved color variations (full-color, black and white). Any changes to the color scheme are not permitted.
- Adding effects – shadows, gradients, or any additional visual effects should not be applied.
- Changing the typography – the logo font should not be modified or replaced with other typefaces.
- Modifying design elements – the DNA strand, architectural motif, and circuit details must remain unchanged. Removing or adding elements alters the logo’s intended meaning.
- Placing on low-contrast backgrounds – the logo must always be placed on a background that ensures clear visibility and readability.

Visual strategy

The visual strategy of the REMEDY project is fundamental to maintaining a consistent and professional brand image across all communication materials. This section outlines the key elements of the project's visual identity, including color palette, gradients, and typography, ensuring clarity, accessibility, and alignment with the project's values.

The color palette is designed to ensure consistency and recognition across all communication materials. The primary color, REMEDY green (#006854), symbolizes sustainability and biofabrication. Dark grey (#262626) and deep red (#680014) are used to provide contrast, emphasis, and visual interest, while reinforcing the project's scientific and technological character.

Figure 7. REMEDY color palette.

In addition to these primary colors, the palette includes extended shades that provide depth and flexibility. These shades allow for varied applications in backgrounds, banners, and graphical elements, ensuring that the branding remains visually engaging without overpowering the primary identity. These extended shades maintain high contrast and legibility, allowing for a diverse range of communication materials while keeping the project's visual identity intact.

By maintaining strict adherence to these color guidelines, the REMEDY project ensures consistency and recognition across all dissemination and communication channels.

Gradient application

Gradients are an integral part of the REMEDY project's visual identity, used to add depth and dynamic contrast to materials such as banners, presentations, and promotional items. The gradient transition blends REMEDY green (#006854) with deep red (#680014), reflecting the project's focus on sustainability and technological innovation.

Figure 8. Gradient usage.

This combination is used strategically in backgrounds, banners, and key visual elements to reinforce the project’s identity. Two primary gradient applications are defined:

- Full gradient background: Used in banners and headers for emphasis and branding consistency.
- Gradient text styling: Applied selectively in presentations and digital graphics to highlight key messages without overpowering the design.

Gradients should be used sparingly to maintain clarity and avoid visual clutter, ensuring that text remains legible and well-contrasted against the background.

Typography

Typography plays a critical role in ensuring that REMEDY materials remain readable, modern, and professional. For formal documentation, Calibri is the primary typeface, ensuring compatibility and readability across software and institutions. For presentations and digital outreach materials, Helvetica (or Arial Nova as an alternative) is used to enhance visual impact and clarity. This typography ensures a cohesive and professional visual identity for all communication materials. By implementing these typography guidelines, the REMEDY project ensures a cohesive and professional visual identity across different formats.

Word document template

To ensure uniformity in formatting, a standardized Word template has been developed for all REMEDY project documentation. The template provides predefined styles and formatting, ensuring clarity, consistency, and alignment with the project's visual identity.

Cover page formatting

The first page of all REMEDY documents serves as the official title page, ensuring a professional and consistent visual identity across all project deliverables. It includes the following elements:

- Project logo – positioned at the top-left corner for immediate identification and brand recognition.
- Document title – left-aligned, written in Calibri, bold, 22 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green).

- Document subtitle (if applicable) – placed directly below the title, using Calibri, bold, 18 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green) to maintain hierarchy and readability.
- EIC logo – located at the bottom-left corner, signifying the project’s affiliation with the EIC Pathfinder program and EU funding acknowledgment.
- Legal disclaimer – a required statement positioned below the EIC logo, ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe guidelines. It states that the document reflects only the author’s view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use of the information contained.
- Visual design elements - two vertical lines on the right side serve as a visual branding element, enhancing aesthetics while maintaining a clean, structured layout. These lines align with the project's graphical identity, reinforcing the structured and modern design approach used across all REMEDY communications.

This cover page layout ensures immediate recognition, compliance with EU branding requirements, and a visually professional first impression for all REMEDY project documents.

Header and footer formatting

To maintain a consistent and professional document structure, a standardized header and footer are applied throughout all pages, excluding the cover page and final page.

Header

- REMEDY project simplified logo positioned on the left for immediate brand recognition.
- Document title aligned to the right, formatted in Calibri, 11 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green) for clarity and consistency.
- Two horizontal green lines aligned to the left, ensuring a structured visual separation.

Footer

- Two horizontal green lines aligned to the right, separating the main content from the footer, enhancing readability and structure.
- Page number placed on the right, formatted in Calibri, 10 pt, #262626 (dark grey) to maintain a clean and professional appearance.

These elements ensure easy navigation, version control, and document identification.

Headings & Subheadings

- Heading 1: Calibri, bold, 20 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green)
- Heading 2: Calibri, bold, 16 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green)
- Heading 3: Calibri, bold, 14 pt, #006854 (REMEDY green)

Body Text

- Font: Calibri, 12 pt, #262626 (dark grey)
- Line Spacing: 1.15 for readability

Table Formatting

Tables are structured to ensure clarity and readability while maintaining a professional appearance.

- Header Row: Background color #006854 (REMEDY green) with white, bold, Calibri 11 pt text.
- Table Content: Two layout options:
Option 1: Alternating row colors (white and light grey #F2F2F2) for improved readability.
Option 2: Uniform white background for a cleaner, more formal appearance.
- Borders: Thin horizontal green lines for structured layout; no vertical borders to maintain a clean look.
- Captions: Italicized Calibri 10 pt, placed above tables

Bullet Point Formatting

- Bullet Style: Dotted bullets (•)
- Bullet Color: #006854 (REMEDY green)
- Text Formatting: Calibri, 12 pt, #262626 (dark grey)
- Indentation: Consistently aligned for clarity and readability

Final Page Formatting

The last page of all REMEDY documents serves as a structured acknowledgment and branding section, ensuring project visibility and compliance with funding requirements.

Elements Included:

- Project logo – centered at the top for strong branding consistency.
- Social media and contact information – positioned below the logo, including the project website (www.eic-remedy.eu), LinkedIn name (REMEDY EIC), official email (remedy@innorenew.eu), and hashtag (#REMEDY).
- Consortium partners' logotypes – positioned in the middle section, ensuring visibility of all participating institutions.
- EIC logo and acknowledgment – represents the project's funding source, including the grant agreement number and a legal disclaimer to ensure compliance with EU Horizon Europe funding communication rules.

- Two vertical lines – a visual design element placed on the right side, maintaining visual alignment with the cover page.

This structured layout ensures a cohesive and professional presentation across all REMEDY project documents.

PowerPoint template

A standardized PowerPoint template has been developed for all REMEDY project presentations to ensure consistency in layout, font, color, and branding. This template guarantees a unified visual identity for the project across conferences, meetings, and other public events. By maintaining a cohesive design, the template helps in delivering professional presentations that align with the project’s branding and communication strategy.

Figure 9. REMEDY PowerPoint template layouts

The template includes several predefined slide layouts:

- Cover/introductory slide:

Serving as both the introductory and closing slide, this slide offers a clear and professional introduction to the presentation. It contains the REMEDY logo on a green background.

- Title slide:

This slide includes the REMEDY project title, along with any additional subtitles or author names. It sets the stage for the presentation by introducing the core details of the project.

- Content slides:

These slides are used for the main body of the presentation, including bullet points, images, and charts. The design ensures clarity and readability with uniform formatting throughout, making it easy to communicate key project information.

- Info slides:

Designed for more detailed content, these slides feature the project name, partner logos, the EIC logo, along with the necessary acknowledgments and legal disclaimers. They allow for the display of partner contributions and funding sources, ensuring proper alignment and consistent formatting.

- Closing slide:

This slide concludes the presentation, featuring the "Let's Innovate Together!" message, along with social media information (website address, email, and hashtag). The EIC logo with acknowledgment and the legal disclaimer are also included.

The PowerPoint template ensures that each presentation is consistent with REMEDY's visual identity by using Helvetica font across all slides and REMEDY green (#006854) for headings and key elements.

Social media

To strengthen outreach and engage a broad range of stakeholders, the REMEDY project utilizes social media platforms for communication and dissemination. By actively participating in key social networks, the project aims to increase its visibility across scientific, engineering, industry, and end-user communities. For this purpose, the project has prioritized LinkedIn as the primary platform for sharing updates, project milestones, and outcomes.

LinkedIn

The official REMEDY LinkedIn account, titled REMEDY EIC, serves as the central social media channel for all project-related communications. This platform will be used to distribute key project deliverables, updates on activities, collaborations, and significant achievements through regular posts and engagement with stakeholders.

Figure 10. REMEDY LinkedIn profile overview

The LinkedIn page for REMEDY EIC can be accessed at:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eic-remedy/>

The types of content shared on the LinkedIn page include:

- Articles and summaries of project deliverables,
- Announcements and recaps of project events,
- News and developments related to REMEDY's ongoing work,
- Publications produced by the project, including both academic and industry-focused literature,

Information on conferences and workshops attended by REMEDY partners,

- Information of project partners and REMEDY project teams,
- Highlights and outcomes from other related EIC-Pathfinder ELM projects.

This LinkedIn profile will be regularly maintained to ensure all stakeholders stay informed about the project's progress, support the dissemination of research findings, and encourage broader engagement with the scientific, industrial, and policy communities.

Additionally, a hashtag #REMEDY was created to categorize content, and making it easier for people to find posts related to the project. It also increases the chances of posts being seen by a broader audience, and it boosts audience engagement.

Each post will also contain tags of project partners, financing bodies and other relevant stakeholders, in order to increase the possibility to share the post and consequently increase the reach.

REMEDY

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